

QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT FOR PUBLIC VALUE OF E-GOVERNMENT IN INDIA

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Abstract

The concept of public value is more and more being used to evaluate the performance of public services (Moore 1995). It is used to measure the total impact of government services to citizens in terms of the value it creates. This concept is enormously valuable for government in improved policy decision making and building a better relationship between government and citizens. In this paper, the concept of Public value has been understood in the domain of E-Government. After extensive review of literature, four major public value creation drivers including (a) Delivery of Quality Public Services, (b) Effectiveness of Public Organizations, (c) Development of Public Trust and (d) Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes are found to be the main determinants for creation of public value of E-Government in India. The questionnaire for these factors has been developed in respect of public value of e-government.

Keywords: E -Government, Public Value, Government to Citizens (G2C), Questionnaire

INTRODUCTION

The concept of public value is more and more being used to evaluate the performance of public services (Moore 1995). It provides a comprehensive framework for examining the performance of public organizations on the creation of public value for citizens (Kelly, Mulgan, & Muers, 2002; Alford & O'Flynn, 2009; Try and Radnor 2007). By using this concept, the performance of public services can be judged with respect to the creation of public value all the way through different sources (Kelly et al., 2002; Try & Radnor, 2007; Moore, 1995).

The domain of this study, however, is e-government in Indian context. E-government puts forward several opportunities for governments to get better the delivery of public services, automate several public services consultation processes, and achieve a broad range of socially

desirable outcomes (Kearns, 2004). With the swift development of e-government, adopting the concept of public value for appraising the performance of e-government from the perspective of citizens is not only suitable but also necessary (Karunasena, Deng, & Singh, 2011).

Applying the above backdrop, this research aims to explore the public value of citizen-centric e-Government in India. The concept of Public value has been understood in general and in the domain of E-Government and applied to identify the major determinates of public value. To demonstrate the purpose of the present study, an extensive and systematic review of literature related to public value of E-Government from various secondary data base has been undertaken. Finally, a model to assess the public value of E-Government in India was proposed on the basis of major public value creation drivers identified through review of literature.

Justification for Preference for the Term E-Government:

The term e-government was first used in the United States in 1993 (Ho, 2002; Heeks & Bailur, 2007). E-Government or ‘electronic government’ is comprised of three main activities: the improvement in efficiency and effectiveness of the functions of government, including the delivery of services to citizens; the increase in transparency of government through the provision of a greater range of information; and the fundamental change in relationship between citizens and public sector organisations (Bellamy and Taylor, 1994; Li, 2003; Watson and Mundy, 2001).

Although the terms ‘e-government’ and ‘e-governance’ in the literature are often used interchangeably, some experts have highlighted the distinction between the two terms. While Satyanarayana (2004) has provided a grammatical distinction i.e. ‘e-governance’ is a verb and ‘e-government’ a noun, Riley (2007) attributes the choice of terms to focus or emphasis by users. According to him, ‘e-governance’ emphasizes the governing process where as ‘e-government’ emphasizes electronic infrastructure. Saxena (2005) has attempted by differentiating the terms ‘governance’ and ‘government’. According to him, while ‘government’ is the institution itself, ‘governance’ is a broader concept –describing forms of governing which are not necessarily in the hands of the formal government.

Review of Literature

Public Value of E-Government - Research Evidence

Kearns (2004), examines the public value of e-government with the help of the three sources of public values creation proposed by Kelly et al. (2002), namely, delivery of quality public services, achievement of socially desirable outcomes, and development of public trust. In this framework, the public value of quality public services delivery is measured by (a) the level of information provision, (b) the extent of e-government use, (c) the availability of choice, (d) the level of user satisfaction, (e) the extent to which e-government services are focused on user priorities, (f) the extent to which e-government services are focused on those most in need, and (g) the cost effectiveness of e-government services. The applicability of this framework is demonstrated all the way through its use in evaluating the public value of e-health initiatives in United Kingdom (Bend, 2004).

Australian Government Information Management Office (AGIMO, 2004) also proposes a methodology for assisting government organisations to evaluate the demand for and the value of e-government initiatives. This methodology facilitates individual agencies to assess the organisational financial value, users' financial value, social value, and governance values created by their online programs.

The European Commission (2006) proposed a different framework for evaluating the public value of e-government. It considered three types of public values, namely, finance, political, and constituency values. Efficiency, democracy and effectiveness are considered as three public values drivers. In this framework efficiency is evaluated by examining the (a) cashable financial gains for public organisations, (b) extent to which public organisation empowers public employees, and (c) improvement of the ICT infrastructure in public organisations. Democracy is evaluated by examining (a) the extent to which public organisations demonstrate openness and transparency through e-government, and (b) citizens' active participation in public sector activities. Effectiveness is evaluated by examining the reduction of administrative burden on

citizens, (b) improvement of citizens' satisfaction, and (c) the extent to which e-government provides more inclusive public services.

Golubeva (2007) extended the framework of Kearns (2004). He proposed a framework to evaluate the public value of e-government portals which includes three main dimensions, namely, (a) quality of public services, (b) public trust, and (c) public policy outcomes. The indicators openness, citizen-centricity and usability have been proposed to measure the public value of public service quality. Transparency and interactivity to measure the public value of public trust. This framework is applied in the Russian Federation for evaluating the public value created through regional portals.

The framework developed by Grimsley and Meehan (2007) to evaluate the public value of e-government. It was focused on (a) services, (b) user satisfaction, (c) trust, and (d) outcomes. The framework takes into account users' experiences on the provision of public services and services outcomes for the development of public trust. The framework reveals that trust is "related to the extent to which the people think that an e-government service improve their sense of being well-informed, gives them greater personal control, and provides them with a sense e-government users experience" (Grimsley & Meehan, 2007, p 134).

The Agency for the Development of Electronic Administration in France proposes a framework for evaluating the public value of IT (Carrara, 2007). This framework examines (a) finance value, (b) social and operation value, and (c) direct customer value. The financial value is measured by examining the financial savings and increase of government's revenue using net present value (NPV) which is a method of calculating the expected net monetary gain or loss from a project, internal rate of return (IRR) which is used to calculate the discount rate which makes the NPV equals to zero (Schwalbe, 2004), and break-even point calculations. The social and operational value is evaluated by assessing the impacts of improved service delivery and employee satisfaction resulting from e-government. Direct customer value is measured by assessing the benefits received by citizens such as service quality, social impacts, cost savings, time saving and so forth.

The framework of Liu, Derzsi, Raus and Kipp (2008) assesses the public sector IT investment by taking into account the multidimensional nature of the value of e-government projects in

European Union member countries. It focuses on the finance value, the social value, the operational value, and the strategic value of e-government projects. This framework is extremely useful for assessing the value of the G2B type of e-government projects.

Karunasena et al. (2011) further extend the framework of Kearns (2004) with the inclusion of effectiveness of public organisations as a dimension of evaluating the public value of e-government. In this framework the public value of effectiveness of public organisations is evaluated by (a) efficiency, (b) accountability of public organisation, and (c) citizens' overall perceptions about the usefulness of the public organisation. The Citizens' trust in public organisations is judged through (a) security and privacy of citizens' information, (b) transparency of e-government services, (c) trust of citizens in e-government services, and (d) participation of citizens in e-government. The public value of public service delivery is evaluated by examining (a) the availability of information, (b) the citizens' perceptions about the importance of the information, (c) availability of multiple channels for accessibility of public services by citizens, (d) cost savings, (e) fairness of the services delivery, (f) citizens' satisfaction on e-government service delivery, and (g) the take-up of e-government services. This framework was used to evaluate the performance of e-government in Sri Lanka with the use of much secondary data.

Omar, Scheepers and Stockdale (2011) propose a conceptual framework for evaluating public value by investigating the quality of e-government service delivery. In this framework, the public value of e-government service quality is examined by considering service quality, information quality, and system quality issues. This framework aims to evaluate public value from the view of citizens, and considers how citizens perceive and evaluate e-government services (Omar et al., 2011).

Karunasena & Deng (2012) proposes a citizen oriented framework for evaluating the public value of e-government with the help of the three sources of public values creation, namely, the delivery of quality public services, the effectiveness of public organizations, and the achievement of socially desirable outcomes through e-government. The delivery of quality public services is measured through Quality of Information, Functionalities of the e-Services and User-orientation. Effectiveness of Public Organisations is measured through Organisational Efficiency, Openness,

and Responsiveness. Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes is measured through Equity, Self-development, Trust, Participatory Democracy, and Environmental Sustainability. This framework has been exemplified by evaluating the performance of e-government in Sri Lanka from the perspective of citizens by using the data from several national surveys. Table 2.7 summarizes the frameworks evaluating the public value of e-government.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In order to answer the above stated questions, the major objectives of the study are to:

- To understand the concept of public value in general and in the domain of e-government.
- To identify the constituents of Public Value in the domain of e-government.
- To develop questionnaire for public value in e-government in India.

Major Drivers Creating Public Value :

Delivery of quality public services

The delivery of quality public services is an important public value driver in e-government (Kearns, 2004). The public value created by the quality of public services delivery through e-government is reflected by the value of (a) information quality, (b) system quality (c) citizen orientation.

The quality of information can be measured through citizens' perceptions about the value of the available information, reflected by the timeliness, relevancy, accuracy, understandability (Wangpipatwong et al., 2009; Papadomichelaki & Mentzas, 2009; 2011), and the level of detail of the information provided (Barnes & Vidgen, 2003).

System Quality originally referred to measures of the information processing system itself and generally reflected engineering-oriented performance aspects (DeLone and McLean, 1992; Negash et al., 2003). Bailey and Pearson (1983) developed and validated items to measure user satisfaction, seven items of which were assigned to measure system quality. Convenience of access, flexibility of the system, integration of systems and response time are examples.

Citizen orientation is about the provision of e-government services in a user friendly manner in order to satisfy users' needs (Jorgensen and Bozeman, 2007; Karunasena and Deng, 2012b). It can also be measured by citizens' perceptions on features such as the Usefulness of frequently asked questions, availability of site maps, presence of simple and concise website addresses (Papadomichelaki & Mentzas, 2009).

Effectiveness of public organizations

Effectiveness of public organizations creates public values (Moore, 1995). This can be measured by efficiency, Reliability, openness and responsiveness. Efficiency is deemed as the ratio of the output to the input of any system. It is concerned with getting maximum benefit with less cost, so it focuses on doing the thing with minimum cost. (Myers et al., 1997).

Reliability refers to the degree to which a promised service provided by an e-government web portal is going to perform by the decided time frame, such as e-mailing or calling the customer, at the same time, the confidence of delivering the right products, and correct charges (Alanezi, 2010). Parasurnaman et al. (1988) declared reliability as one of the most important dimensions in SERVQUAL instrument.

Openness is the transparency of public services (Jorgensen & Bozeman, 2007). This indicates the extent to which an organization discloses the processes of decision making and dealings and performance information in a timely manner (Wong & Welch, 2004).

Responsiveness refers to the degree to which the services offered by an e-government web portal is really helpful and there is no delay beyond the time frame in replying to citizens. Online users wait for the organization to respond to their queries without delay (Yang, and M. Jun, 2002) immediate response will assist e-government users to make decisions faster, answers their questions and resolves their problems (Alanezi, 2010). The public value of the responsiveness through e-government can be examined by considering citizens' perceptions about the value of public organisations' timely responses to their inquiries made through e-government channels (emails, forms available online on websites etc) (Decman, 2007; Gauld et al., 2009 ; West, 2004;).

The development of public trust

The development of public trust between citizens and government is a key dimension for examining the public value of e-government (Heeks, 2008; Kearns, 2004). It can generally be evaluated from the viewpoint of security and privacy of citizens' informations (Kearns, 2004; Carter and Belanger, 2005); trust of citizens in e-government and trust in internet has been taken up from the Web Trust Model (WTM) (McKnight et al., 2002; Belanger et al., 2002; Gefen et al).

Achieving socially desirable outcomes

Achieving socially desirable outcomes is a major source of creating public value through e-government (Kearns, 2004; Heeks, 2008). The achievement of socially desirable outcomes is replicated by the deliverables, consequences and impacts that public services are designed to attain or have (Cole & Parston, 2006) including equity, level of corruption , e-democracy , self-development of citizens, and environmental sustainability.

Equity refers to the availability of resources for all, and the protection and promotion of varieties of culture, particularly within minority communities (Benington, 2009). To ensure equity, e-government applications must avoid the exclusion of some groups in the society due to factors such as the lack of skills and resources, disability, income disparities, geographic locations, etc. The self-development of citizens is another important public value created through e-government (Jorgensen & Bozeman, 2007; Karunasena & Deng, 2012b). It measures whether citizens can learn and develop their skills through various e-government initiatives like e-learning, improvement of ICT literacy skills, expansion of network skills and so forth (UNDESA, 2003).

In the context of e-government, democracy can be assessed by examining the extent to which citizens' views expressed through e-government are taken into account in the decision making (Machintosh, 2004). Participation is an area of democracy (Machintosh, 2004). Participation in e-government refers to citizens' taking part in decision making by providing feedback on government policies using various e-participation applications such as virtual meetings, cyber campaigns, feedback pools, and public survey tools (Anttirioko, 2003).

Corruption can be broadly defined as the abuse of public power for the benefit of private individuals. The introduction of ICT can reduce corruption by humanizing the enforcement of rules, lessening the discretion of officials, and increasing transparency. However e-government

reduces corruption through information publicizing, instant monitoring, preventing and control, and data sharing (Oye, N. D 2013).

E-government applications can bring many environmental benefits through energy saving, limiting duplication of efforts, sharing data and resources by automating repetitive tasks, reducing the use of paper (ITU, 2008). Public value of environmental sustainability can be measured through citizens perceptions on the value of saving energy, limiting the duplication of effort and resources, sharing data and resources, reducing the paper use, reprocessing consumable equipments (ITU, 2008; Molla, Cooper, and Pittayachawan, 2009).

Questionnaire Development:

Stage 1: Domain Identification

A 1: Content Analysis (Public Value Construct)

This research has employed the common technique of content analysis in order to capture the dimensions of e-Government Public Value from an extensive review of the literature (Weber, 1985). Three rounds of literature review and analysis were conducted. The following table shows the main and sub dimensions of Public Value of e-Government along with the corresponding sources from the first round of literature review.

First Round Review: Frameworks evaluating the Public Value of e-Government,

S.No	References	Main Factors of public value	Sub Factors
1	Karunasena & Deng (2012)	Delivery of quality public services, Effectiveness of public organizations, Achievement of socially desirable outcomes	Quality of Information, Functionalities of the e-Services , User-orientation, Efficiency, Openness, Responsiveness. Equity, Self-development, Trust, Democracy, Environmental Sustainability
2	Omar, Scheepers and Stockdale (2011)	Service quality, information quality, system quality issues.	quality of e-government service delivery, citizens perception,
	Karunasena et al.	Public service delivery, Development of Trust ,	The availability of information, citizens perceptions , multiple channels , cost

3	(2011)	Effectiveness of Public Organisation , Achievement of Outcomes	savings, fairness , satisfaction, take-up trust in public organizations security and privacy , transparency , participation of citizens in e-government efficiency, accountability , citizens' overall perceptions
4	Liu, Derzsi, Raus and Kipp (2008)	finance value, social value, operational value, strategic value	Assesses the public sector IT investment by taking into account the multidimensional nature of the value of G2B type e-government projects.
5	Carrara, (2007)	finance value, social and operation value, direct customer value	Savings, revenue, Service delivery and employee satisfaction. service quality, social impacts, cost savings, time saving.
6	Grimsley and Meehan (2007)	Services, user satisfaction, trust, Outcomes.	greater personal control, and provides them with a sense e-government users experience”
7	Golubeva (2007)	Quality Of Public Services, Public Trust, And Public Policy Outcomes.	quality of public services, is measured by openness, citizen-centricity and usability public trust : Transparency and interactivity
8	The European Commission (2006)	Efficiency (Financial and Organisational Value) Democracy (Political Value) Effectiveness (Constituency Value)	Cashable financial gains, employee's empowerment, ICT infrastructure. Openness and transparency, citizen's participation. Administrative burden on citizens, satisfaction, inclusive public services.
9	AGIMO, (2004)	organizational financial value, users' financial value, social value, and governance values	Proposes a methodology for assisting government organizations to evaluate the demand for and the value of e-government initiatives.
10	Kearns (2004),	Quality Public Services Achievements of Outcomes Development of Trust	- Level of information provision, - Level of e-government use, - Availability of choices - Level of user satisfaction - Focused on user priorities Fairness - Cost savings
11	Kelly et al. (2002),	Delivery of quality public services, Achievement of socially desirable outcomes, Development of public trust	The public value of quality public services delivery is measured by (a) the level of information provision, (b) the extent of e-government use, (c) the availability of choice, (d) the level of user satisfaction, (e) the extent to which e-government is focused on user priorities,

			(f) The extent to which e-government is focused on those most in need, and (g) the cost effectiveness of e-government services.
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On the basis of literature analysis as shown in the above table, the four main factors were identified . The detail with their sources is given in table below.

Main Factors of Public Value Evaluation		
Sr. No	Main Factor	Sources/References
1	Delivery of Quality Public Services (DPS)	Omar, Scheepers and Stockdale (2011), Karunasena et al. (2011), <i>Kanishka Karunasena, Hepu Deng (2010)</i> , Grimsley and Meehan (2007), Golubeva (2007), Kearns (2004), Kelly et al. (2002),
2	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASO)	Karunasena et al. (2011), <i>Kanishka Karunasena, Hepu Deng (2010)</i> , Grimsley and Meehan (2007), Golubeva (2007), Kearns (2004), Kelly et al. (2002),
3	Development of Public Trust (DPT)	Karunasena et al. (2011), Grimsley and Meehan (2007), Golubeva (2007), Kearns (2004), Kelly et al. (2002),
4	Effectiveness of Public Organisations (EPO)	Karunasena et al. (2011), <i>Kanishka Karunasena & Hepu Deng (2010)</i> , The European Commission (2006)

Second Round Review: Sub Factor Analysis

After the first round of review, further literature review was conducted using the references from the first round and the main factors of public value were used as the basis for second round literature review. The focus was to identify sub-factors corresponding to the main factors of public value of e-Government.

Sub-Factors of Public Value of e-Government	Issue / comment	Source / Reference
Cost, Time, Avoid Personal Interaction, Control, Convenience, Personalisation	E-Government G to C study. Measurable variables (validated and pilot tested).	(Gilbert et al., 2004)
Time, communication, personalisation,	E-Government G to C study. Measurable variables (validated and pilot tested).	(Kolsaker and Lee-Kelley, 2008)

information retrieval, well-informedness, participation		
Control, trust, wellinformedness	E-Government G to C study. Develops aframework to evaluate e-Government projects.	(Grimsley and Meehan, 2007)
Trust	E-Government G to C study. Develops Trust as essential enabler for e-Government.	(Warkentin et al., 2002)
Trust, reliable information	E-Government G to C study. Develops Trust as an outcome variable.	(Welch et al., 2005)
Well-informedness, information availability	E-Government G to C study. Relates information availability with transparency.	(Thomas and Streib, 2003)
Well-informedness, Trust, Participate in decision-making, Communication	Inspect s the use of ICT for citizens.	(Coleman, 2004; Coleman, 2005)
Productivity, decision-making, time	General e-Government community-based study. looks at benefits to citizens of an e-Government community project	(Bowonder et al., 2005)
Time, job simplification	E-Government empirical G to C study. Studies the perceived benefits for citizens.	(Wang and Liao, 2008)
Timeliness, Citizen involvement, self development, equity, trust	The study is focused on general administration and society. Generate spheres of influence where public values can be identified. Creates inventory of public values for each sphere.	(Jorgensen and Bozeman, 2007)
Time savings	The study is general e-Government based on government/citizen. Recommends a cost benefit model for evaluating services.	(Andersen and Medaglia, 2008)
Time savings, cost savings	E-Government G to C study. Focused on e-Government tax filing.	(Tan and Pan, 2003)
Cost and time savings	E-Government G to C study. Focused on e-Government tax filing.	(Fu et al., 2004; Fu et al., 2006)
Better communication, efficiency, reduced costs	Focus of study is general e-Government. Net benefits validated through survey on government respondents.	(Brown, 2007)

Financial (cost savings), Ideological (information access), Stewardship (trust)	Government focused study. Proposes a public ROI assessment framework.	(Cresswell et al., 2006)
Communication, involved in decision making	E-Government G to C study. looks at the impact of e-Government on trust, communication and participation.	(Tolbert and Mossberger, 2006)
Citizen involvement	E-Government G to C study. Evaluates web site quality.	(Barnes and Vidgen, 2003)
Time and cost saving, improved equity, personalisation, transparency, participation, trust	Government focused study . An OECD project for assessing benefits of e-government projects.	(Lau, 2006)
Cost savings, Avoid Personal Interaction, personalisation, communication, transparency, trust	Government focused Case study on e-Government tax filing.	(Gonzalez et al., 2007)
Time savings, cost savings, value added services (e.g. personalisation), transparency (information availability)	Government /citizen-based study . suggests a framework and methodology for setting up indicators and metrics of quality and performance.	(Gouscos et al., 2007)
Satisfaction, Trust	Government focused discussion paper by UK government on Public Value. emphasizes key results values.	(Kelly et al., 2002)
Transparency (information availability and involvement in Government), convenience, time, cost savings	E-Government G to C study. Emphasizes values in citizen-government interaction using e-Government.	(Marche and McNiven, 2003)
Enhanced democracy	E-Government G to C study. Focus of study is	(Olphert and

and participation	e-Government design. studies benefits of citizen participation.	Damodaran, 2007)
Improved transparency and interactivity	General e-Government study. Benchmarking levels of transparency and interactivity available on government web sites.	(Pina et al., 2007)
Improved citizen interaction	General e-Government study Evaluating the impact of e-Government on service effectiveness.	(Reddick, 2006)
Improved transparency and interactivity	General e-Government study. Benchmarking the levels of transparency available from government web sites.	(Wong and Welch, 2004)
Greater service accessibility, efficiency (avoid personal interaction), trust, improved participation	General e-Government study Based on secondary Data. Examines the impact of e-government on various outcomes.	(Yang and Rho, 2007)
Customisation (personal needs)	General e-Government/ecommerce study . employs ACSI data to compare predominantly satisfaction measures between e-government and e-commerce web sites.	(Morgeson and Mithas, 2009)
information quality, system quality, service quality	E-Government G to C study. Measures knowledge and courtesy of employees, physical facilities and accuracy of the system.	Wangpipatwong et al. (2009)
content, interactivity, ease-of-use, functionality, reliability, trust.	E-Government G to C study. It identifies the achievement of socially desirable outcomes through e-government as an important source of public value without showing how to measure these outcomes.	Papadomichelaki and Mentzas (2009, 2011)
Medium of response, Degree, No of Days (TAT)	General e-Government study . evaluating how e-government has increased the responsiveness of public organisations .	Decman,(2007) ; West (2004)
availability of email addresses, Time taken, Degree, auto responses,	General e-Government study , examined by considering citizens' perceptions about the value of public organisations' timely responses	Gauld et al. (2009),

Time taken to reply, Over all Quality of response	to their inquiries made through e-government channels (emails, online forms in webistes etc)	
responsiveness to people with disabilities.	The study reveals that state websites and web portals generally do not recognise the needs of those with disabilities in their website designs. Failing to consider issues of accessibility in designing websites make e-government disadvantageous for people with disabilities	Rubaii-Barrett & Wise, 2008
efficiency and effectiveness , Improving democracy, enhancing trust, ensuring equity	General e-Government study . evaluating how development of value for citizens is possible through e-government,	Kunstelj & Vintar, (2004); Heeks (2008a).
multilingual content	Multilingual/Local language content in their websites for those who do not speak English to ensure equity through e-government.	West (2004),
information protection (Trust)	Citizens expect their information to be protected by public authorities	Jorgensen & Bozeman (2007)
privacy and security		Kearns, (2004);
Corruption & openness, Increases the transparency	Reducing corruption and increasing openness of public sector. e-government has had a positive impact on corruption reduction at public organizations	Shim and Eom (2008); Anderson (2009); Jaeger & Bertot (2010);
limit duplication of effort and resources, share data and resources, automate repetitive tasks, centralise tasks and services, increase the efficiency in the sharing resources, decrease the use of paper, to dematerialise	Environmental impact of E-Government, measures how E-government applications can bring many environmental benefits.	ITU (2008)
service quality, information quality, and system quality	Measures public value of e-government, proposes a framework, aims to evaluate public value from the view of citizens, and considers how citizens perceive and evaluate e-	Omar, Scheepers and Stockdale (2011)

	government services	
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Third Round Review: Sub Factor Identification/Development

As a result of second round review and on the basis of targeted specific piece of information, a final third round of literature review was conducted. Following this process, the distinct sub-factors of public value identified and grouped against their main factors. The output of this whole process resulted in 15 sub-factors representing to 4 main factors of public value presented in the table below:

Sub-Factors	Definition	Main Factors	Source (s)
Information Quality	Citizens' perceptions about the value of the available information	Delivery of Quality Public Services (DQPS)	Barnes & Richard (2006); Gupta and Jana (2003); Hussein et. al. (2007); Ibrahim et. al (2014); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); McKnight et. al (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Siriluck Rotchanakitumnuai (2008); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); Wang pipat wong <i>et al.</i> ; (2005); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010)
System Quality	originally referred to measures of the information processing system itself and reflected engineering-oriented performance aspects	Delivery of Quality Public Services (DQPS)	Barnes & Richard (2006); Hussein et. al. (2007); Ibrahim et. al (2014); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); McKnight et. al (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Phang et.al (2006); Taylor and Todd (1995); Teo et al (2008); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010); Wang & Liao (2008); Wangpipatwong <i>et al.</i> ; 2005;
Citizen Orientation	The provision of e-government services is in a user friendly manner in order to satisfy users' needs	Delivery of Quality Public Services (DQPS)	Ibrahim et. al (2014); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Kim <i>et al.</i> ; (2009); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008); Moufeed et al (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Parasuraman et al. (2005); Pitt et al (1995); Sareen et. al

			(2013); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010);
Efficiency	The ratio of the output to the input of any system.	Effectiveness of Public Organizations (EPO)	Kolsaker & Lee Kelly (2008); McKnight et al (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Parasuraman et al. (2005); Pathak et al; (2012);
Reliability	The degree to which a promised service provided by an e-government web site is going to perform by the promised time	Effectiveness of Public Organizations (EPO)	Kolsaker & Lee Kelly (2008); Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011); Parasuraman et al. (2005); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010)
Openness	The extent to which an organization reveals its decision processes and procedures and performance information in a timely manner	Effectiveness of Public Organizations (EPO)	Anderson (2009); Bhatnagar (2003); Jaeger & Bertot; (2010); Karunasena & Deng (2012); La Porte et al.; (2002); McKnight and Chervany (2001); Phang et.al (2006); Shim & Eom; (2008); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010);
Responsiveness	The degree to which the services provided by an e-government web site is helpful and there is no delay in responding to citizens	Effectiveness of Public Organizations (EPO)	Alanezi <i>et al.</i> ; (2010); Decman; (2007); Gauld et al.; (2010); Karunasena & Deng; (2010a); Karunasena & Deng (2012); McKinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011); Parasuraman et al. (2005); Pitt et al (1995); Shareef <i>et al.</i> ; (2011); Siriluck Rotchanakitumnuai (2008); Teo et al (2008); West; (2004);
Security and Privacy	Confidence that The e-Government website has adequate security features .personal and transactional	Development of Public Trust (DPT)	Barnes & Richard (2006); Economides & Terzis (2007); McKnight and Chervany (2001); Moufeed et al (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011); Phang et.al

	information are protected		(2006); Pitt et al (1995); Shareef et al (2011); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010) ; Wangpipatwong <i>et al.</i> ; (2005);
Trust in e-government	Trust on e-Government portal for conducting government transactions	Development of Public Trust (DPT)	Alawneh A. et al. (2013); McKnight et. al (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011); Teo et al (2008);
Trust in Internet	Confidence that encryption and other technological advances on the Internet make it safe to transact there.	Development of Public Trust (DPT)	McKnight et. al (2002); McKnight and Chervany (2001); Moufeed et al (2011); Phang et.al (2006); Schaupp & Carter (2010); Shareef <i>et al.</i> (2011); Teo et al (2008);
Equity	The availability of resources for all, and the protection and promotion of diversities of culture, especially within minority communities	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	Gamage & Halpin (2007); Edmiston (2003); European Commission (2006); Karunasena & Deng (2010a); Kuzma (2010); Rubaii-Barrett & Wise (2008); Smith (2001); Stowers (2008); Subramanian & Saxena (2008); West (2004);
Self-Development	Citizens can learn and develop their skills through various e-government initiatives such as e-learning, improvement of ICT literacy skills, and so forth	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	European Commison (2006); Evans & Yen (2006); Karunasena & Deng; (2010); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Phang et.al (2006); Porter; L.W. (1963); United Nations (2010) ; Van Deursen & Van Dijk (2009);
E-Democracy	The extent to which citizens' views expressed through e-government are taken into account	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	Anttirioko (2003); Coleman (2004); Karunasena & Deng; (2010); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008); Macintosh (2004); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); United Naitons (2005);

	in the decision making		
Corruption Reduction	E-Government reduces corruption through information publicizing, instant monitoring, preventing and control, and data sharing	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	Bhatnagar (2003); Ibrahim et. al (2014); Jana and Gupta (2003); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Pathak et. al (2012); Sapanjeet Kaur & Kamalkant (2012);
Environmental Sustainability	Citizens perceptions on the value of saving energy, limiting the duplication of effort and resources, sharing data and resources, reducing the paper use, recycling consumable equipments	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	ITU (2008); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Lim & Tang (2007); Molla et al. (2009);

Table: Summary of main factors and their sub factors

S.No.	Main factors	Sub Factors
1	Delivery of Quality Public Services (DQPS)	Information Quality, System Quality, Citizen Orientation.
2	Effectiveness of Public Organizations (EPO)	Efficiency, Reliability, Openness , Responsiveness
3	Development of Public Trust (DPT)	Security and Privacy, Trust in e-government and Trust in Internet
4	Achievement of Socially Desirable Outcomes (ASDO)	Equity, self-development, e-democracy, corruption reduction, environmental sustainability.

Development of Questionnaire for Public Value of e-Government

Questionnaire Indicators and sources

Information Quality

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Relevant to need	Information provided by e-Government Web site meets my needs
2	Up – to – date	Information provided by e-Government Web site is up – to – date.
3	Accurate	Information provided by e-Government Web site is accurate
4	Sufficient	Information provided by e-Government Web site is sufficiently complete for my needs

Source : [1] Moufeed et al (2011); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); Wang pipat wong *et al.*; 2005; Karunasena & Deng (2012); Gupta and Jana (2003); McKnight et. al (2002);

[2] Ibrahim et. al (2014); Hussein et. al. (2007); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Lee et. al (2002); Siriluck Rotchanakitumnuai (2008); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); McKnight et. al (2002); Nabafu and Maiga (2012);

[3] Barnes & Richard (2006); Ibrahim et. al (2014); Hussein et. al. (2007); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Lee et. al (2002); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

[4] Barnes & Richard (2006); Hussein et. al. (2007); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); Wangpipatwong *et al.*; 2005; Karunasena & Deng (2012); McKnight et. al (2002); Verdegem and Hautekeete. (2010)

System Quality

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	User friendly	The e-Government system is user friendly.
2	Easy to use	The e-Government system is easy to use.
3	Easy to navigate	I find the e-Government website easy to navigate.
4	Any time & anywhere.	The e- Government website can be accessed at any time and from anywhere.

Source: [1] Hussein et. al. (2007); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

[2] Barnes & Richard (2006); Hussein et. al. (2007); Lopez-Sisniega (2009); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Teo et al (2008); Wang & Liao (2008); Wangpipatwong *et al.*; 2005; McKnight et. al (2002); Phang et.al (2006); Taylor and Todd (1995)

[3] Barnes & Richard (2006); Ibrahim et. al (2014); Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); **Parasuraman et al. (2005)**; McKnight et. al (2002); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010)

[4] Ibrahim et. al (2014); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010); Nabafu and Maiga (2012)

Citizen Orientation

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Links to other web sites	The e-Government website contains links to other web sites that citizens may be interested in.
2	FAQs	Frequently asked questions (FAQs) are available on e-Government website
3	Simple web address	The address of the website is simple .
4	Multilingual	The information provided on e-Government website is in different languages.

Source : [1] Kim *et al.*; 2009); Moufeed et al (2011); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Melitski; J. et.al (2005); Nabafu and Maiga (2012);

[2] Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[3] Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[4] Ibrahim et. al (2014)

Efficiency

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Simple & structured	The e- Government website is simple to use; structured properly; and requires a minimum of information to be input by the customer
2	Transparent and speedy	The e-government system has removed intermediary agents between the user and the government bringing in more transparency and speed to the system.
3	Save time and	The users can save time and money by sing the e-Government systems

	money	for government services.
4	Efficient	The e- Government website is efficient in fulfilling your needs of interaction with the government agency.

Source : [1] Parasuraman et al. (2005); McKnight et. al (2002);

[2] Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Pathak et. al; (2012);

[3] Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Phang et.al (2006);

[4] Moufeed et al (2011); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008);

Reliability

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Reliable	E-Government website is reliable in terms of Correct technical functioning and accuracy of service delivery and information.
2	Executable	This e-government site performs the service successfully upon first request.
3	Default browser	This e-government site works properly with your default browser.

Source : [1] Parasuraman et al. (2005); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008); Verdegem and Hautekeete. (2010)

[2] Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011)

[3] Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011)

Openness

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Drafts & regulations	Public policy drafts; laws or regulations are available online for public consultation
2	E-Complaint	Citizens make complaints online
3	Contact information	Display staffs contact information online
4	Organizational information	Display organizational charts; duties and responsibilities of public sector staff.

Source : [1] La Porte et al.; (2002); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Phang et.al (2006); McKnight and Chervany (2001);

[2] Jaeger & Bertot; (2010); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[3] La Porte et al.; (2002); Karunasena & Deng (2012); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010) ;

[4] La Porte et al.; (2002); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

Responsiveness

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Quick response	The e-Government website responds very quickly to citizen's request.
2	Online web link	The e-Government systems have online link for citizens to request for any help.
3	Citizen charter	Display citizen charter online (citizen charter specifies the minimum number of days that a public organization takes to process or deliver a service)
4	Case tracking	Online case tracking (ex: status of an application submitted to a government organization)
5	Automatic responses	Automatic responses to online submissions and emails

Source : [1] Alanezi *et al.*; 2010; Mc Kinney; Yoon; And Zahedi (2002); Moufeed et al (2011); Parasuraman et al. (2005); Pitt et al (1995); Shareef *et al.*; (2011); Teo et al (2008);

[2] Siriluck Rotchanakitumnuai (2008)

[3] Karunasena & Deng; (2010a); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[4] Karunasena & Deng; (2010a); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[5] Decman; (2007) ; Gauld et al.; (2010); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

Security and Privacy

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Safety	I feel safe to complete my transaction with e-Government website
2	Web security	The e-Government website has adequate security features
3	Information secrecy	The e-Government website does not share my personal information with other site.
4	User hesitation	I would hesitate to provide information to the e-Government website
5	Transaction security	Acquisition of username and password in this e-government site is secure.
6	Data security	Data provided by users in this e-government site are archived securely.

Source: [1] Barnes & Richard (2006); M.A. Shareef et al (2011); Pitt et al (1995); Verdegem and Hauttekeete. (2010) ; McKnight and Chervany (2001); Phang et.al (2006);

[2] Economides & Terzis (2007); M.A. Shareef et al (2011); Moufeed et al (2011); Wangpipatwong *et al.*; (2005);

[3] Barnes & Richard (2006); Kumar et al. (2007); M.A. Shareef et al (2011); Moufeed et al (2011);

[4] Shareef et al (2011);

[5] Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011)

[6] Papadomichelaki; X.; Mentzas; G. (2011); Nabafu and Maiga (2012);

Trust in e-government

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Government actions	I feel that government acts in citizen's best interest.
2	E-Government portal	I always feel confident to rely on Indian national e-Government portal for conducting government transactions
3	Interaction	I always feel confident that I can rely on government to do their part when I interact with them
4	Obligations	I am comfortable relying on the government to meet their obligations

Source: [1] Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

[2] A. Alawneh et al. (2013);

[3] Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

[4] Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

Trust in Internet

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Structures	I trust that legal and technological structures adequately protect me from problems on the Internet.
2	Safeguards	The Internet has enough safeguards to make me feel comfortable using it.
3	Encryption	I feel confident that encryption and other technological advances on the Internet make it safe for me to transact there.

Source: [1] Moufeed et al (2011); Schaupp & Carter (2010); Shareef *et al.* (2009); Shareef *et al.*(2011); Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

[2] Schaupp & Carter (2010); Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002); Phang et.al (2006); McKnight and Chervany (2001);

[3] Teo et al (2008); McKnight et. al (2002);

Equity

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Physically challenged	Websites which comply with the accessibility standards to support people with special needs (ex: hearing; visual problems)
2	Local language	Availability of e-government initiatives in native languages
3	Socially disadvantaged	E-Government services for socially disadvantaged groups
4	Kiosks	The availability of kiosks in rural areas

Source: [1] (Rubaii-Barrett & Wise (2008); Kuzma (2010);

[2] Smith; 2001; West; 2004; Stowers; 2008; Karunasena & Deng; 2010a);

[3] European Commission; (2006)

[4] Edmiston (2003); Gamage & Halpin (2007); Subramanian & Saxena (2008)

Self Development

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Training for Citizens	Availability of training for citizens which enable them to improve digital; information and strategic skills
2	ICT Resources	ICT resources for facilitating the improvement of citizens' skills;
3	Personal Development	Learning to use e-government gives me opportunity for personal development
4	Self-Fulfillment	Learning to use e-government increases my feeling of self-fulfillment
5	Accomplishment	Learning to use e-government gives me a feeling of accomplishment

Source: [1] Van Deursen & Van Dijk (2009) ; Nabafu and Maiga (2012);

[2] Evans & Yen (2006); European Commison (2006); United Nations (2010); Karunasena & Deng; (2010);

[3] Phang et.al (2006); Porter; L.W. (1963);

[4] Phang et.al (2006); Porter; L.W. (1963);

[5] Phang et.al (2006); Porter; L.W. (1963);

E-democracy

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Information alert	Government keeps you informed about upcoming policies that affect you through websites (ex: online news letters; bulletin boards)
2	E-Discussion	The citizen can participate online in public discussions and policy making
3	Participative decision	The government takes your opinion for actual decision making

Source: [1] Macintosh (2004); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008);

[2] Anttirioko (2003); (sri lanka theses); Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008); Nabafu and Maiga (2012); Karunasena & Deng; (2010);

[3] Kolsaker & Lee kelly (2008);

Corruption Reduction

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Greasing the palm	The e-Government service removes any potential under table cost to get the service
2	Red tapism	The e-Government service reduces the bureaucratic process.
3	E-Complain	Enabling citizens to report problems and resolve complaints online through e-government system has reduced corruption.
4	Public exposure	e-government is a kind of punishment for the corrupt through public exposure
5	Fear of exposure	e-government Creates discouragement for corruption by creating fear of exposure
6	Actors against corruption	Bring the different actors together in fight against corruption

Source: [1] Ibrahim et. al (2014);

[2] Ibrahim et. al (2014); Pathak et. al; (2012);

- [3] Sapanjeet Kaur & Kamalkant (2012)
- [4] Bhatnagar (2003)
- [5] Bhatnagar (2003)
- [6] Pathak et. al; (2012);

Environmental sustainability

Sr. No	Questionnaire Indicator (s)	Indicator Question (s)
1	Limit duplication	Developing e-government applications which help to limit duplication effort and resources
2	Energy saving	Switch off computers; printers and other ICT equipment when not needed (energy saving)
3	Reduce paper printing	Reduction of paper printing (double side printing; use electronic copies)
4	Recycling consumable	Recycling consumable equipment (ex: papers; ink cartridges etc)

Source: [1] ITU (2008); Molla et al. (2009); Karunasena & Deng (2012);

[2] Karunasena & Deng (2012); ITU; 2008; Molla et al. (2009)

[3] Karunasena & Deng (2012); ITU; 2008; Molla et al. (2009)

[4] Karunasena & Deng (2012); ITU; 2008; Molla et al. (2009)

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